

Sufism and Human Resource Managers

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Abstract

Sufism is understanding and guidance to be on the right track. Sufi can be defined as noble Muslim with direct experience of nature Violence, tolerance, law and orders, human resources management, administration and justice could be softly improved with the teachings, beliefs and practices of Sufism. The post modernism theories are spread to wide areas of life and cover the fields of philosophy including a guideline to managers of human resources in maintaining the high spirits of the employees. This research paper emphasizes on the human values, organizational behavior, leadership and motivation among all tiers of the employees. A character and value from different behaviors is selected to get the results for the required study. The behavior and social norms already set by Sufis are supportive in having the control of the organization. The paper is divided into eight parts. Part one gives introduction, part two is study rationale, part three is study analysis, part four is on research analysis, part five is on results and parts six, seven and eight are recommendations, conclusion and references.

Keywords: Sufism, postmodernism theories, Human resources, motivation and organization behavior.

1. INTRODUCTION:

This study is based upon the guidelines set by Sufis in the light of post modernism theories' benefiting manages of Human Resources. Sufism may be described as Islamic ways of thinking which helps peoples of different walks of life to attain nearer of nature and get better results. It outlines four fundamentals principles of Repentance, Sincerity, Remembrance and Love. Human Resources management is workforce of the organization which is called 'Human Capital' where the knowledge and skills are commanded.

The ten million dollar question is how to get the work done from individuals as per your choice, which seems to be most difficult task; it has been observed that mostly people dodges and looks busy but doing nothing! Or hardly one only works under continuous supervision; even most of the time the motivation theories and leadership styles fails! But all those managers are successful who have also adopted Sufi teachings. The first thing is 'Time' as Sufis were allowing time for nature and its creatures, whereas today's manager has no time to conduct proper meetings have systematic trainings, to develop consensus, to reach at excellent conclusion.

The Sufis were calm, courteous and down to earth and they preached for right practices, so the Human Resources Manager does in managing the life cycle, organizational behavior as well as administrating employees. Post modernism theories penlights understanding of human values, characteristics, social norms and the power of attitude, soft spoken words and care exercised to fellow people.

2. STUDY RATIONALE:

The essence morale is explored to urge love, discipline and sincerity in our thoughts and practises. Teaching of Sufism is to find means and ways to please the creature by helping the mankind. The Human Resource Management also works on their lines to guide people to get work done with pleasure. All teachings of Sufism set a straight path to the HR managers as to be a good compassion and love people, always touch the heart of the people. Intellect and love are made with different materials, intellect ties people in knots and love dissolves all tangles. Most of the work problems are related from linguistic mistakes and misunderstandings. Words are not taken as study the universe and apply all theories to human beings. Always look at the end of the process. Try not to resist changes and allow ups and downs in life. Select the way of treating others as you like for yourself. A true Sufi is one, when un-justifiably accused, attached and condemned, face all situation patiently and neither utters a single bad word nor blame to focus on Humans and results.

3. STUDY ANALYSIS:

Sufism is based on four pillars as:

- i) 'Shareea't', to follow the Islamic teachings and laws;
- ii) 'Tareekat' means to get some 'Murshid' or guide;
- iii) 'Marfatt' which is to know the procedure and coordinate; and
- iv) 'Haqeeqat' the union and reality.

The Sufis life encourages the Human Resource Manages to transform their working, fill it with love and get desired results. As per teachings of Moulana Jalal-ud-Din Rumi "One can study God through everything and everyone in the universe because God is not confine in a mosque, synagogue or church, but if you are still in need of knowing where exactly His abode is there is only one place to look for Him which is in the heart of a true lover", this leads to a practicing manager to set the environment of the organization to get work done in a best effective way and get competitive advantage; in addition this helps to maximize employee performance in service of an employee's basic and long run objectives. Sufi thoughts support the Human Resource Management in managing people and utilization of workforce.

Whereas, Human Resource Management is tackling of Human Resources problem, to achieve more and retain employees, improvement in performance, increase in growth, involvement to yield high productivity, quality of work, best approach to do jobs; and right engagement of employee. Due to rising importance of the Human Resource Management and total quality management practises to develop a competitive advantage and raise the ability to complete in the market place, organizations must understand how to attract, retain, and motivate the skilled Human Resource. In addition, an organization should be good at implementing total quality management soft dimensions, in order to create competitive advantage over time. Purpose of this paper is to review the literatures that have examined the effect of Human Resource Management practices, total quality management practices on competitive advantage.

4. RESEARCH ANALYSIS:

Conduct of this study focus is on two main Human Resource Management problems, the maximum output from an employee and positive change in his behavior with the teachings of Sufism. Analysis is done according the prospective of post modernism theories to explore behavior pattern of Sufis like M/s Jalal-ul-Din Romi, Shah Abdul Karim and Shah Abdul Latif Bhitai. The Sufi who gave information and set guidelines are the texts of above saints' novels. Textual analysis is the method used in different fields like cultural studies, sociology, philosophy, literature, etc. This is mostly used in qualitative research which helps the researcher to collect the required data about characteristics and help to get knowledge about different traits of their personalities.

5. RESULTS:

- i) Employee behaves differently due to different culture, manager just see ten percent, which is above the surface and visible i.e. behavior, while ninety percent of employee is below the surface and invisible i.e. attitudes and beliefs. Manager must make a sense of Sufi and make behavioral changes.
 - ii) National culture has influence over corporate culture and mostly compromises are done on performances but with addition of Sufi thoughts, one can bring positive changes.
 - iii) Culture comes from the top like Sufis, big bosses to also try to get time to meet lower grade employees and coach them.
 - iv) This research guides for ways and means to create a better understanding with the Human Resource Management and it may also guide as how to establish a pure sense of belonging as employees to own ideas and work on it.
 - v) Sufi thoughts enable managers to re-examine themselves to reduce resistance faced in completion of tasks.
 - vi) Everybody has due respect and conventional managers will also contribute and take efforts for results, if they are properly respected.
 - vii) Actually it shall be very clear in mind, whom we are leading; whether to give instructions or to produce problem before them as they to give solutions; then advise them to implement, by taking and implementing their ideas, actually we will be creating a good sense of ownership.
 - viii) Human Resource Management is to build trust, inspire teamwork, facilitate and support team decision, expand team capabilities, create team identity, encourage and utilize team differences, forces and influence change.
 - ix) Role of manager is to respect every employee, put problem in front of others, respect their ideas, try to develop consensus and implement the decision as the others to realize that their idea is taken up.
 - x) We often tell solutions - What other don't own! Instead of solutions, mention problems, obtain solutions and tell them to implement.
 - xi) Manager's role is to coach the team and give them spirit and courage.
 - xii) The success of team could be seen when the leader leaves the team and team still continue to perform as when Adeeb Rizvi or Sattar Edhi will leave their Institutions, after such personalities/leaders.
 - xiii) Mostly teams' fails as neither the team members own the instruction nor leader moves!
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- Leader just pass orders from his office. Actually he has to move, he has to leave the comfort zone and come to un-comfort zone. He has to work with team.
- xiv) Team must be very clear that organization's graph will comedown, if they will not bring changes and new things or new ways of achieving goals.
 - xv) For change one must start from himself, innovation is to develop, adopt or implement idea for product, process, business model (easy paisa) into commercial success by delivering value.
 - xvi) Innovation in organization is mechanism which requires changing technologies, concern needs, modes of competition and improving efficiency.
 - xvii) Every organization have a white space i.e. challenge for manager to train people to operate in a way of new business like iPad, ATM machine, Gillette Razor, coffee shops with all brands perfumes etc.
 - xviii) Besides doing routine work at-least one hour in a week (fix time as 2 ~ 3 pm on every Thursday) for developments.
 - xix) If we not change employees; not prepare them for change, openness to team; opportunity is to be missed. Change always faces lot of resistance of old mind set and Manager have to develop can do attitude.
 - xx) What does the Olympic gold medalist do; what others don't do.
 - xxi) Actually innovators do what other do not; it is questioning, observing, networking (new idea and listening), experimenting and associating.
 - xxii) As a team leader, in beginning of meetings create conflict and after making team create unity.
 - xxiii) To involve whole team.
 - xxiv) Senior people to be part of the team.
 - xxv) Entire team is to be involved in goal setting.
 - xxvi) Being junior in team be more courteous and try everyone to speak.
 - xxvii) Decide time line (but don't rush), take time to reach at conclusion.
 - xxviii) Develop some external link.
 - xxix) Team to discuss issues in a way as all to feel equalness.
 - xxx) Team crisis could be handled by travelling together; self and other could be known learned when in problem as character is defined when in crisis.
 - xxxi) Creativity in the workplace is personal attitude for change, management support for continual change, development resistance to work deep for results.
 - xxxii) To move teams effectively managers have to move from his position, he has to respect every member of team and their care; he has to get solutions not directly implement his orders.

6. RECOMMENDATIONS

- 1) **Personal objectives:** To provide necessary career developed and job related education opportunities and maintaining employee satisfaction.
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II) Human Resource Management works through dedicated managers at some lines what Sufis worked for day-to-day execution of HR related functions. The HR manages can set objectives with the guideline of Sufism as under:

- i) **Social objectives:** Measure put into place that respond to the ethical and social needs or challenges of the company as employees for equal opportunities, etc.
- ii) **Organizational objects:** To help to enhance efficiency of the organization, including training and maintaining high retention rate.
- iii) **Functional objectives:** Guidelines for proper person for proper job and its full utilization with its potentiality.

III) SUFI AND HUMAN RESORUCE MANAGER MODEL

SUFI	HUMAN RESOURCE MANAGER
Need mentor	Need of staff/personnel.
Guide	Determine Do's and Don'ts
Behavior	Train and upgrade learning to employees
Personality	Supervise and guide employees
Focused	Evaluate the work
Thinking force	Establish discipline and work culture

Set personal examples	Avoid polices in office
Soft spoken	Apply HR software to the ease of work
Caring	Manage employee relations
Show them road to success	Prepare employee benefits policies
Equality	Real with discrimination
Help everyone	Ensure equal opportunities
High morale	Motivate employees
Calm and confident	Mediate disputes.

7. CONCLUSION:

Human Resource Management governs relationship of organization with its employees. This term was first used in 1900, and then more widely in 1960s. Human Resource Management theories may be new but follows Sufi sayings and the goal is to make effective use of employees, it manages people within organizations mission and reinforce the culture. In recent years, a number of people who focus on business and on HR's contribution to the organization performance but HR has never been more necessary the today! The effort to achieve excellence, focused learning, quality, teamwork and reengineering get things done easily through following Sufi culture, these are fundamental HR issue. As such, HR manages have to create an entirely new role and agenda that is not traditional HR activities by focusing outcome. As Sufi take a common man on right path and how HR manages couldn't focus on the job only. HR manages should have to be partner with all line manages, he has to be expert and champion for employers to increase employee contribution and will continuously transform to improve organization's capacity for change. No doubt! This could be a new agenda for HR manages.

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